

The Threat of Cross-Sea Understanding Drones to State Defense Systems

(Case Study in the Indonesian Region during 2020)

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Abstract: *The phenomenon of underwater drones crossing national borders may be something that is hot to discuss, this is based on the discovery of an underwater drone belonging to China by fishermen near the island of Selayar. This incident suddenly caused a stir in the community because the function of the drone itself is usually to find and record information, activities and events as well as for reconnaissance functions. The phenomenon of the discovery of foreign-owned underwater drones has not only happened once or twice, but has been found several times in Indonesian waters in recent years. So, is the phenomenon of underwater drones crossing the Indonesian border that can interfere and become a threat to the national defence system? With a qualitative research approach that uses the case study method, it is hoped that later it can produce an answer to these problems. This study uses a threat theory approach and a state defence system to be able to find out whether underwater drones are really a real threat and can disrupt the national defence system. The results of this study are that underwater drones can become a threat and disrupt the national defence system if the drone crosses national borders (enters the territory of the Indonesian state) without permission. The threat of underwater drones crossing Indonesia's maritime boundaries can be a threat because of the work of the drones themselves that can be used to spy and transmit data in real time to the control centre.*

Keywords: Threat, Drones, National Defense System

I. INTRODUCTION

Drones which is commonly known as an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and controlled remotely is one type of technology that is currently very popular with various circles of the world with different types of needs. Drone technology (unmanned aircraft) was originally designed with the aim of being a military tool by the North Atlantic Treaty Organizations (NATO) in the 18th century for reconnaissance and spying activities (Finda, 2017). Witny, (in Finda, 2017) describes several reasons why drone technology is very popular in supporting various military activities, including the minimal risk in carrying out dangerous missions, a high level of efficiency of use and lower production costs compared to manned aircraft.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is a type of aircraft that is controlled by a remote control system via radio waves. UAV is an unmanned system (Unmanned System) which is an electro-mechanical-based system that can perform programmed missions with the characteristics of a flying machine that functions remotely by the pilot or is able to control itself, the UAV can be controlled manually via radio control or automatically by processing data on sensors (Hardy, 2018).

Often technological developments, drones/unmanned aircraft which are usually used in the air, have now also targeted underwater areas and are better known as underwater drones or Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) or sea gliders. Similar to the purpose of developing aerial drone technology in general, underwater drones are developed with the function of monitoring, whether in the fields of research, agriculture, civil, industrial, or to support military activities (Finda, 2017).

Tim (2008) in his writings divides Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) into Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs), Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), and Remotely Operated Towed Vehicles (ROTVs). Argos (in Stephen, 2009) explains that the Underwater drone (sea glider) is designed for deep waters where the vehicle can

traverse a large area with minimal energy use and is specifically designed for the needs of Blue Water scientists, who require greater control over the vehicle (Argos buoy profile). The free-float that scientists often use has no control capabilities other than vertically descending and rising in the water column. The newest Argos buoy model cycles to a depth of 2000m every 10 days, with a lifetime of 4-5 years for each instrument).

In recent years, the phenomenon of the entry of drones into Indonesia has occurred several times. According to a report by The Guardian (2021), there have been three underwater drone findings that have crossed Indonesia's maritime boundaries. The first finding occurred in March 2019, namely the discovery of China's Sea Wing UUV (Unmanned Underwater Vehicle) in the Riau Islands which incidentally directly borders the South China Sea. The next one was in January 2020 in East Java, and the most recent one was at the end of December 2020 in the Selayar Sea, South Sulawesi.

The phenomenon of the discovery of the first underwater drone in Indonesia is the discovery of a drone that occurred in Bintan, Riau Islands in March 2019. This drone was found floating by a fisherman from Tenggel Island, Kab. Bintan at sea at around 06.00 am. Then the 2 m long drone was pulled to the shore and reported to the local police. This was also confirmed by the Head of the Bintan Police, AKBP Boy Herlambang, that there were reports from residents who found foreign objects in the form of missiles with Chinese writing on them. The drone was then secured for a few days at the East Bintan Police Headquarters for investigation which was then handed over to Lantamal IV Tanjungpinang and sent to Jakarta for further investigation (Kurnia, 2019).

The next phenomenon of the discovery of underwater drones is the discovery of underwater drones by fishermen from the Masalembu Islands, Kab. Sumenep, Madura, East Java. The fisherman found a strange object similar to a missile (drone) in the middle of the sea in the waters of Masalembu which is about two miles away. The foreign object was found with its tip on top, which was then pulled to the beach. From the information of residents who saw the object, it was known that this drone was yellow, weighed more than 1 meter long and contained Chinese writing. On this drone there are also cables, cameras, bolts in the middle and ends, and there is a red button at the end.

Worried that the strange missile-like object would explode, one night later, the drone was again swept into the waters of the Masalembu sea. The incident of the drone discovery that occurred in mid-January 2020 was also confirmed by the Head of the Sumenep Police Public Relations Sub-section, AKP Widiarti S (Putri, 2020).

Finally, the phenomenon of the discovery of a drone that was warm a few months ago occurred when a fisherman was searching for fish in the Selayar Sea, South Sulawesi Province. Arriving around a rock, the fisherman found an object that had an antenna, because he felt there was something strange about the object, the fisherman tied the object with a rope and pulled it to the beach. Then the fisherman also asked for help from local residents to lift the object which weighs about 175 kg to the mainland who then finally reported and handed the object over to the military (TNI) Koramil 1415-03/Pasimarannu (Faturrohman, 2020).

From the conference of the Chief of Naval Staff Admiral (KASAL) TNI YudoMargono, the object was taken to the Hydrographic and Oceanographic Center of the Navy (Pushidrosal). From the research, it was stated that the tool is a Sea Glider (underwater drone) which has the characteristics of a main frame made of aluminum, with each wing measuring 50 cm and body length measuring 225 cm. This object also consists of a propeller with a length of 18 cm and has a rear antenna with a length of 93 cm. In addition, this object also found a camera-like instrument located on the body, and in general there was no indication of the characteristics/writings of the country of origin.

Through this conference, the Chief of Naval Staff Admiral (KASAL) TNI YudoMargono explained that these underwater drones are commonly used for oceanographic research or researching deep ocean conditions such as taking temperature measurements, measuring conductivity (to calculate salinity), measuring current speed and direction, chlorophyll fluorescence measurements, optical backscattering measurements, and seabed depth measurements.

The discovery of this third drone is different from previous discoveries that occurred in January 2020 and March 2019, because this underwater drone was found still in a state of light complete with camera, GPS, pressure and tilt sensors, magnetic compass, and piston which was then immediately investigated. by the Indonesian military. The three phenomena of the discovery of these drones then gave rise to various speculations from various levels of society, whether this was done purely for underwater research, intelligence surveys/illegal research, or for military purposes and spying on Indonesian waters, considering the findings of the three drones were found in Indonesian sea, which is far from China and occurred in a period of only 2 years.

Several cases of the discovery of these drones indirectly have had an impact and unsettled the community. Judging from the main function of this drone itself which is usually used for monitoring or spying. This is clouded because the three drone findings were concluded to come from the same country, namely China (Zhafran, 2021). Of the three cases of finding underwater drones belonging to China, of course, it is considered that there are urgent reasons and interests that make the Chinese state continue to deploy drones in Indonesian sea areas.

The phenomenon of the discovery of drones that occurred in the last 2 years is certainly a form of disturbance to Indonesia's territorial sovereignty and the state defense system, especially if China's spying activities and crossing

Indonesian sea/territorial boundaries are carried out without permission from the government to enter and conduct monitoring operations in Indonesian seas. This is also a serious threat that must be considered by the government in protecting the territorial waters of Indonesia from foreign spies.

Based on Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense, which is explained in Article 4, what is meant by a threat is every domestic and foreign business and activity that is considered to endanger the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the country, and the safety of the entire nation. Meanwhile, according to Law Number 17 of 2011 concerning State Intelligence Article 1 paragraph 4, threats are every effort, work, activity, and action, both from within and outside the country, which is judged and/or proven to endanger the safety of the nation, security, sovereignty, territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and national interests in various aspects, whether ideological, political, economic, socio-cultural, as well as defense and security.

The phenomenon of drones crossing Indonesia's maritime boundaries and originating from China is a form of threat from abroad that can endanger the sovereignty and integrity of the country and disrupt the safety of the entire nation. The entry of foreign drones into Indonesian territory is considered to be able to disrupt the stability of the Indonesian state defense system.

According to Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning State Defense Article 1 paragraph 2, the State Defense System is a universal defense system that involves all citizens, territories and other national resources, and is prepared early by the government and organized in a total, integrated, directed, and continuous manner to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation from all threats. Meanwhile, state defense according to Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning State Defense Article 1 paragraph 1 is all efforts to defend the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state.

From the background of the findings of several cases / phenomena of drone discovery that occurred in Indonesian waters in the last 2 years, the researchers formulated problems and limited the research, namely by analyzing how underwater drones work, explaining how the function and use of underwater drones are, uncovering the causes. other countries send underwater drones to Indonesian waters, and analyze how underwater drones affect Indonesian waters and how much this will become a threat to the national defense system.

II. METHOD

In this study, researchers conducted research using a qualitative approach to examine how the impact of threats that could be posed by underwater drones crossing Indonesia's maritime boundaries on the Indonesian state defense system. The method used to support this research is case study and interview methods, both primary and secondary data disbursement interviews.

Case study

The case study research technique referred to in this study is to study and explore the phenomena of the discovery of underwater drones in Indonesian waters, and how these phenomena can occur in Indonesia. To strengthen this research, the interview method was also carried out with the aim of obtaining data on how underwater drones work and what are the functions of these underwater drones.

Primary data

According to Amiruddin (in Finda, 2017) primary data is data obtained directly from the first source related to the problems to be discussed. Sources of data obtained from the field directly with interviews. The interview technique carried out here is by conducting interviews through information media to informants (by looking at related party conferences with Indonesian news media/online through the related news media YouTube channel.

Secondary Data

Meanwhile, secondary data according to Marzuki (in Finda, 2017) are data obtained from books as complementary data for primary data sources. The secondary data sources of this research are data obtained by conducting a literature review such as scientific books, research results and so on. Secondary data includes documents, books, research results in the form of reports, and so on. The books that become secondary data sources are books, journals, and writings about drones, underwater drones, threats and state defense systems. To complement the primary data source, the researcher added readings about the drone from several related articles and journals.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When compared to submarines, the use of underwater drones to support marine military activities (navy) is arguably very profitable. From the difference in weight, underwater drones can freely operate in the deep sea because of

their smaller field of movement, and this is of course a distinct advantage for the country that owns it to carry out reconnaissance operations in areas where submarines cannot move freely, and because of their low weight. This small size means it is also unlikely that this underwater drone will be detected by sonar owned by a country's marine security ships. From how it works, seaglider drones / underwater drones or also called Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs), are divided into two types, namely Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs), Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). ROVs are underwater vehicles that are operated remotely and connected by cable or wireless. While AUVs are underwater vehicles that can operate independently.

From several cases of the phenomenon of finding UUVs that have been described previously, the latest discovery of underwater drones that occurred in Selayar is included in ROVs because objects

Source: Morten (2009)

Controlled remotely (from the ship) owned by a foreigner. The general way underwater drones work is that they are lowered into the sea using a ship, then the drone slowly descends to a certain depth within a certain duration of time and speed (for the case of drones found in the Selayar sea, it descends to a depth of 2000m for 6 hours at a speed of 10m/d). s.

Then the object floated with the current for 9 days, after which it returned to a depth of 2000m. It is when hovering and diving in the sea that this underwater drone conducts reconnaissance / spying and retrieves Indonesian underwater data. After reaching that depth, the drone will then pump oil from the storage area which will then make the drone float. This underwater drone floats to the surface for up to 12 hours to transmit data to the control center via satellite. This type of underwater drone can last up to 4-7 years once operating in the ocean.

Like drones in general (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles/UAVs) that can be used for various needs and aspects of life, Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) can also perform the same activities. For example, to support civilian activities, such as shipping goods or to reach the outer islands that are difficult to reach. In the fisheries and marine industries, this underwater drone can be used for mapping underwater areas with high marine intensity/products, and measuring the level of underwater natural gas content. In addition, the presence of drones will be able to help fishermen and sea transportation to find out areas of the deep sea that have a strong current, so it is not recommended to be traversed. For the field of Education,

While in the military field, with underwater drones, of course, activities that can be supported include observing / spying, where from the seabed drones can track a country's fleet of marine defense forces, defense technology fleets used by a country, and to spying on activities or military training activities that have been planned or are being carried out by a country, and which includes danger, namely to measure the depth of the sea that cannot be detected by the sonar technology of ships over the sea, so that this can later be used to enter submarines or any other undersea spy drone.

As is known, the phenomenon of the discovery of underwater drones that occurred in Indonesia occurred in the Riau Islands, East Java, and in the Selayar Sea, South Sulawesi. The three drones, when viewed from their trajectory, were found in one of the world's busiest routes, the "Malacca Strait", and also around the Sunda Strait and Lombok Strait. These three routes are very important travel routes for China, because these three routes are the gateway for oil from the Middle East to China. When viewed from the geographical conditions, the three routes are the only deep waterways that can connect the South China Sea to the Indian Ocean.

According to Sutton (in Muhaimin, 2021) routes such as the Sunda Strait and the Lombok Strait will be very important in times of war. This is also another basis for the intelligence gathered by these underwater drones to be of great value to the Chinese Navy if the country intends to use the strait as a passage for its submarines.

Source: Muhaimin (2021)

Based on the Geneva Conventions of 1958 concerning the territorial sea and additional routes, there are several rights of passage of foreign ships against a country, namely the matter of peaceful passage through the territorial sea/straits, there is no right of air passage, and through the strait may not be suspended. Furthermore, based on the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) the sea area is divided based on the type of trajectory, which include peaceful passage, transit passage, archipelagic sea lane crossing, and access and communication traffic.

Peaceful passage is a passage area through the territorial sea and islands to pass from one part of the high seas or the Exclusive Economic Zone to another part of the high seas. Foreign ships can pass peacefully if they do not conflict with security, order and peace. This is stated in UNCLOS articles 18 and 19, Law no. 6 of 1996 concerning Indonesian Waters article 11 paragraph (3), and Government Regulation no. 36 of 2002 concerning Peaceful Crossing Article 2.

Next is the transit crossing, where on this trajectory, foreign countries have freedom of flight for the purpose of transit (crossing) which occurs continuously and as quickly as possible. This transit crossing usually occurs in the Straits area used for international shipping. This transit route is passed to cross the waters that connects one part of the high seas (EEZ) to another part of the high seas (EEZ). This is as stated in the international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) article 38 concerning the right of transit passage, article 39 concerning the obligations of ships and aircraft during transit passage, and article 40 concerning research and survey activities.

Archipelagic sea lane passage (ALKI) is a passage where foreign ships and aircraft can exercise the right of archipelagic sea lane passage for shipping or flights from parts of the high seas (EEZ) to other parts of the free sea (EEZ) by crossing the territorial sea and archipelagic waters. Indonesia. this is stated in Government Regulation no. 37 of 2002 article 2. In this sea passage (ALKI) also foreign ships and aircraft exercising the right of archipelagic sea lane passage must immediately pass through or fly over the archipelagic sea lanes in the normal way, and only for transit. occurs continuously, immediately, quickly and unhindered. (Government Regulation no. 37 of 2002 article 4). In this ALKI sea,

Due to the ratification by the Indonesian government on the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS), as a consequence Indonesia must give the international community the right to traverse the Indonesian archipelagic waters. If Indonesia does not then stipulate archipelagic sea lanes, foreign ships and aircraft can traverse the routes commonly used for international navigation.

In Law no. 6 of 1996 concerning Indonesian waters, it is explained that all foreign ships and aircraft have ALKI rights (article 18 (2)). The Indonesian government determines sea lanes and flight routes that are suitable for the exercise

of the right of passage for ALKI by foreign ships and aircraft (article 19 (1)). Furthermore, in the explanation of article 19 (6) it is stated that government permits are required for ships and aircraft that sail or fly in the airspace of ALKI.

The 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) also explains that the instruments in international law are submarines, warships, government ships used for non-commercial purposes, and other tools applied in marine scientific research. So from this sentence it can be concluded that Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) are a form of ship that has been regulated in the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS).

With the phenomena of finding underwater drones that cross the boundaries of Indonesia's territorial sea, this indicates that Indonesia's marine territory is very strategic and it is possible that there are many parties who know what is in it, considering that Indonesia is a country located between Two Continents and Two Oceans.

From the phenomena found by China's underwater drone, this is of course an illegal act because it does not have a permit from the country being crossed (in this case through Indonesian waters) and of course it has violated the boundaries of Indonesia's sovereignty / sea area which is protected by the Indonesian government. the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) which was ratified by Law No. 17 on the Ratification of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea. The 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) clearly states that the operation of Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) in Indonesian waters, without permission and violating peaceful passage, can be considered detrimental to the peace, order or security of the Republic of Indonesia. for collecting information that is detrimental to the defense or security of Indonesia (article 19 (2)). In addition, these phenomena are also considered to have violated the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS) article 40 which states that every transit passage with active research and surveying must have a permit.

With the illegal activities carried out by foreign/Chinese Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) that carry out reconnaissance/spy and information gathering that cross the boundaries of Indonesian marine waters, of course this can interfere with sovereignty and become a threat to the system. Indonesian defense. This is because the war that will occur in the future or modern war is an information war, where the winners in this war are those who have data and information. This is as stated by military and defense observer Connie Rahadikundini Bakrie in an online interview which states that the winners in modern wars or future wars are those who have the information. TNI Commander Marshal HadiTjahjanto also stated in a press conference that future wars or modern wars will rely heavily on technology and information. Where if a country is able to even collect various data and information on other countries (target countries) in war, then later that country will be able to easily attack, control and even destroy the country that is the target / target.

IV. CONCLUSION

The phenomenon of the discovery of foreign objects or underwater drones, better known as Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) is a new phenomenon for the Indonesian people, this is because these three phenomena have occurred in the last 2 years, and the peak phenomenon of the discovery of underwater drones that occurred at the end of last year (December 2020) in the Selayar Sea, South Sulawesi Province. From the research results of the Indonesian Navy's Hydrographic and Oceanographic Center (Pushidrosal), a fact was found that the underwater drone was used for oceanographic research and research used to examine ocean conditions in Indonesian waters such as measuring conductivity, speed and direction of currents, measuring fertility levels. underwater, optical backscattering and seabed depth measurements.

From the workings and capabilities of underwater drones / Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) which can last up to 4-7 years in one operation at sea, then of course this is a technological breakthrough that is very reliable and has a high level of efficiency, where in addition to can be controlled remotely, only by using this object a country can carry out reconnaissance / spy activities without having to fear being detected because this object can operate in the deep ocean to a depth of 2000m.

The phenomenon of the discovery of Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) that occurred in Indonesia, is a case that should be suspected, this is because the discovery of the three drones which were found in three different routes and these three routes are important for the international community, especially China, because This route is the only route / gateway that can connect China and the Middle East as one of the largest oil-producing regions in the world. This route is also becoming increasingly important, because if a country can control and control the route, then that country will be able to control the world economy.

This factor is also one of the reasons why the Chinese state in recent years seems very aggressive in conducting expeditions towards the south, both to the South China Sea and to the waters / deep seas of Indonesia. In addition, the importance of information is also one of the reasons why China conducts reconnaissance / spying using its underwater drone technology, this is also one of the keys in the future, where the war that will occur in the future is no longer an open war involving many vehicles. and the armed forces fleet, but in this modern war will use a lot of technology and

information, and the key to be able to win the modern war is a country that has data and information against other countries. With this information and data,

With several phenomena of cases of illegal entry of foreign drones without permission into the territorial waters / deep sea of Indonesia which in this case is a drone belonging to the Chinese state, of course this will be a threat to the national defense system and of course this has also violated the boundaries of the sovereignty area. Indonesia's deep waters/seas which are actually also protected by the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS). So indirectly, the illegal entry of foreign drones (Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs)) belonging to China into the territorial boundaries of Indonesia's deep waters/seas This has violated article 40 of the 1982 international law of the sea convention (UNCLOS), which states that every transit passage with active research and surveying must have a permit.

For this reason, the Indonesian government in this case should take firm action both by taking diplomatic and legal steps, as well as strengthening the national defense system, especially the maritime / underwater defense system in Indonesian waters. Diplomatic steps that need to be taken include maritime diplomacy by optimizing soft power in dealing with regional threats and increasing cooperation both bilaterally and multilaterally in the maritime sector. Furthermore, through maritime security by preparing hard power to strengthen Indonesia's maritime defense forces in an effort to secure Indonesian territory. Taking decisive steps can be carried out by sending a diplomatic protest against the country concerned, in this case, China. Other than that,

Furthermore, to strengthen the national defense system, in this case the government through the Ministry of Defense, the Ministry of Transportation, the Ministry of Communications and the TNI as well as various other related Ministries and Institutions, should strengthen and establish an underwater / maritime-based defense system to monitor all traffic activities. underwater traffic, either by installing devices that can detect movements in the air (drones), on the surface, underwater and in various strategic locations, as well as by establishing an underwater defense system (fortress) that can perform underwater monitoring and control. directly.

With it is proven that there is a clear and real threat from the phenomenon of the discovery of the entry of Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) into the territorial waters/deep sea in Indonesia, further research needs to be done to develop a strategy that can and should be implemented. implemented to prevent and deal with the real threat posed by the entry of illegal underwater drones belonging to foreign countries.

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